

management was conducted with transplanted Jaya rice on Tarai soil in the lowlands of Uttar Pradesh, India, during the 1977-78 wet season. Total nitrogen used was 60 kg/ha as ordinary urea, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea-enriched farmyard manure (FYM), urea incubated with soil, and pellet application of urea incubated with soil. Single superphosphate and muriate of potash at 40 kg P₂O₅/ha and 25 kg K₂O/ha were basally applied to all plots.

Differences in grain yield due to source and timing of N application were significant. Nitrogen use was most efficient with SCU broadcast as a single application and incorporated into the soil before transplanting (see table).

Effect of timing of application and source of nitrogen (N) on grain yield of rice. Pantnagar, India.

Planting	N application (kg/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha)
	Early tillering	Late tillering	Panicle initiation	
0	0	0	0	4.9
60	0	0	0	6.4
15	15	15	15	6.9
0	30	0	30	6.4
0	20	20	20	6.5
30 ^a	15 ^a	0	15 ^a	6.5
30 ^b	15 ^b	0	15 ^b	6.4
60 ^c	0	0	0	7.1
30 ^c	15	0	15	7.0
30 ^d	15 ^d	0	15 ^d	6.3

S.E m± 0.2

CD at 5% 0.6

CV (%) 7

^a Urea incubated with soil. ^b Pellet application of urea incubated with soil. ^c Sulfur-coated urea.

^d Urea-enriched farmyard manure.

Fertilizer and weed management of aus rice in Bangladesh

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Inadequate weed and fertilizer management hampers aus (monsoon) rice production in Bangladesh.

A 1979 experiment in the BRRZ

project area used the improved variety Chandina under farmer conditions to determine: 1) the yield gap between the potential and the farmer's actual yields, 2) the effectiveness of nitrogen, sulfur, and weed control on yield, and 3) the economics of alternative practices. The design was complete factorial in a randomized complete block, with three applications, each with nitrogen, sulfur, and weed control. The crops were grown with supplementary irrigation.

Yield with the farmer's practices (2.6 t/ha) and potential yield (4.3 t/ha) showed a gap of 1.7 t/ha (see table). The use of nitrogen, sulfur, and weed control bridged the gap by 0.7, 0.6, and 0.7 t/ha, respectively. The change brought in a net income of US\$415/ha. The benefit-cost ratio for the extra investment ranged from 5.3 to 16.4, depending on the treatment combinations. ■

Agroeconomics of nitrogen, sulfur, and weed management over farmer's levels in BRRZ cropping systems research site at Salna, Bangladesh, 1979 aus.

Treatment ^a			Av yield (t/ha)	Yield difference from farmers' level (kg/ha)	Value of yield difference (US\$/ha)	Cost of H inputs (US\$/ha)	Added profit over farmer's treatment (US\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Nitrogen	Sulfur	Weeding frequency						
F(54 kg/ha)	F(0)	F(zero)	2.6	—	—	—	—	—
F	F	H(3)	3.0	401	106.93	7.87	99.06	12.6
F	H(34 kg/ha)	F	3.1	440	117.33	14.53	102.80	7.1
F	H	H	3.2	532	141.86	22.40	119.47	5.3
H(80 kg/ha)	F	F	3.1	453	120.80	7.20	113.60	15.8
H	F	H	3.3	686	182.93	15.07	167.87	11.1
H	H	F	4.1	1419	378.40	21.73	356.67	16.4
H	H	H	4.3	1669	445.06	29.60	415.47	14.0

^a F = farmer's level of management (traditional system), H = improved management (improved variety).

Modified urea materials and nitrogen efficiency in wetland rice

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The growth and yield of wetland rice

depend on the availability and use of nitrogen at the various physiological stages of the crop. Split application, placement, and controlled release are the three major approaches to increasing nitrogen efficiency in wetland rice. Five seasons of experimentation at Mandya have shown that the basal application of nitrogen in mudballs, paper capsules, and

as supergranules and sulfur-coated urea is superior to split application.

In a replicated trial conducted in the summer of 1979 under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), basal application of several modified urea materials was compared with basal and split applications of prilled urea. Granulated compost and super-

Effect of sources and timing of nitrogen application on the grain yield of rice variety Rasi (IET 1444). Mandya, India, 1979 summer.

Treatments ^a B - T - PI	Yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./m ² x 100)	1000-grain wt (g)
0 - 0 - 0	3.0	260	161	20
60 - 0 - 0	5.4	342	233	22
30 - 0 - 30	4.6	340	217	23
30 - 30 - 0	5.2	332	245	21
0 - 30 - 30	3.4	270	204	21
60 ^{nc} 0 - 0	4.6	302	209	20
60 ^{fym} 0 - 0	3.1	228	163	19
60 ^{SG1} 0 - 0	6.1	373	294	20
60 ^{SG2} 0 - 0	5.6	394	298	21
60 ^{GC} 0 - 0	6.3	413	304	22
CD (0.05):	0.7	-	-	-

^aB = basal; T = tillering; PI = panicle initiation; nc = urea blended with neem cake; fym = farmyard manure enriched with urea; SG1 = supergranule (1-g size); SG2 = supergranule (2-g size); GC = granulated compost.

granules gave the highest grain yields (see table). High panicle production and high grain number accounted for the increased yield. Urea blended with neem cake (using coal tar) and farmyard manure

enriched with urea did not give superior performance. The lack of a clear response to split application could have been caused by the short growth duration (120 days) of the test variety. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Rice ratoon crop management in hilly regions of Karnataka, India

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Ratoon cropping might increase rice production without an increase in land area. Reports of good ratoon crop yields in the hilly regions of Karnataka and farmers' acceptance of ratoon cropping have encouraged researchers to evaluate the potential for increasing and stabilizing rice ratoon yields and to identify optimum management practices. A preliminary study on ratoon cropping was therefore undertaken in a farmer's field.

Two replicated experiments were

conducted to determine the effect of cutting time and cutting height. A third experiment continued the yield performance study conducted in 1978. All studies were conducted with the stubble of the 1978 wet season harvest at Sringeri, Chikmaglore District, which is representative of the hilly rice region. In the first experiment cutting time was fixed at 35, 40, and 45 days after 50% flowering (40 days is the normal harvest time). The net plot size was 10 m² with 3 replications in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). The main crop seeded on 30 June and cultivated with farmers' practices was cut, leaving a stubble height of 13 cm on 13, 18, and 23 December. The entire experimental area was topdressed with 50 kg urea/ha

Table 1. Effects of cutting time after 50% flowering and cutting height of the main crop on the grain yield of the ratoon crop of variety Intan.

Days after 50% flowering	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	Cutting ht (cm) from ground	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)
30	3.0	8	2.8
35	3.1	13	2.9
40	3.1	18	2.6

^aCV: 13%. ^bCV: 21%.

(44% N) 30 days after the second treatment (18 Jan 79). In the second experiment, cutting heights were 8, 13, and 18 cm above the ground, and a RCBD was replicated 4 times. The net plot size was a direct-seeded 2-m row. The main crop seeded on 30 June and managed with farmers' practices was cut on 23 December 1978 and topdressed with 50 kg urea/ha 30 days later. The third experiment, located at Balehonnur, repeated the 1977 experiment.

The main crop seeded on 23 June 1978 was cut on 9 December and the ratoon was topdressed 40 days later at 40 kg urea/ha. The ratoon was harvested on 21 April 1979. The other practices followed were local ones. All 3 experimental crops lost an estimated 35% to birds (there were no rice plots around the experiments).

Neither the cutting time nor the cutting height influenced grain yield (Table 1). A 5-day interval after harvest seems to be too short to cause significant yield differences because the main and ratoon crops have long growth durations (171 and 130 days). Longer cutting intervals might cause significant differences. Similarly, the yield differences attributable to cutting height were not significant, but treatments differing by 10 cm or more might produce large differences. With the late-maturing variety Intan, minor differences in cutting time and height of the main crop appear to have no significant influence on yield.

Table 2. Yield data of main (MC) and ratoon crops (RC) of Intan at Balehonnur, Karnataka, India, 1978-79, at different fertility levels.

MC treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Yield of RC (% of MC)
	MC	RC	
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	4.2	2.1	50
N ₄₀ P ₀ K ₀	5.2	2.6	50
N ₈₀ P ₀ K ₀	5.3	2.1	51
N ₁₂₀ P ₀ K ₀	5.9	2.5	42
N ₄₀ P ₂₀ K ₀	5.3	2.7	51
N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₀	5.7	2.8	49
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₀	6.0	2.9	48
N ₄₀ P ₂₀ K ₂₀	5.4	2.8	52
N ₈₀ P ₄₀ K ₄₀	5.7	2.8	49
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀	5.7	3.5	61
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₄₀	6.1	3.4	56
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₄₀ + Zn	6.2	3.1	50
Mean	5.6	2.8	50